

Impact Study

Conservation

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Context

[One million species](#) are threatened with extinction due to factors like deforestation, climate change and loss of habitat. Effective conservation of biodiversity requires comprehensive data about species distributions, population trends and ecosystem health. Without accessible and integrated biodiversity data, conservation efforts risk being poorly targeted, duplicated, or even missing critical areas entirely.

This case study demonstrates how biodata resources have enabled more effective conservation strategies, from national-scale biodiversity assessments to community-driven monitoring programmes.

Recovering from environmental disasters

A major barrier to biodiversity research and conservation planning efforts is the fragmentation and inaccessibility of biodiversity data. This is typically collected and housed across a range of different organisations like museums, universities and government departments — often in incompatible formats.

The [Atlas of Living Australia \(ALA\)](#), was established in 2007 as a national effort to make biodiversity information accessible and usable. The initiative has been tackling conservation by means of its online database of over 150 million records, covering specimens from natural history collections, field observations and surveys. An [evaluation of the ALA](#) demonstrates its significant impact on culture change, including increased open sharing of data and standards. The evaluation also conservatively estimated that the ALA delivered a 3.5:1 return on investment.

The role of the ALA was especially important in the context of the recovery efforts from the [2019-2020 bushfires](#). ALA provided a [national dataset of bushfire-affected areas](#), called the National Indicative Aggregated Fire Extent Dataset, which mapped the areas burned across Australia. This dataset was developed by the Australian government and used by ALA to show which regions and habitats were impacted by the fires. It helped identify priority species and affected ecological communities for targeted management and recovery. In particular, the ALA data and mapping tools [enabled researchers, conservationists and policymakers](#) to assess the spatial impact of fires on wildlife and vegetation by overlaying the extent of the fires with species occurrence records before and after the fires. This spatial biodiversity information shaped recovery priorities and interventions.

Working with government bodies such as the Threatened Species Commissioner, [scientists](#) used ALA data (combined with recent [IUCN Red List Assessments](#) and species observation records from [DAWE's Species Observation System](#) (SOS) and [BirdLife Australia](#) to prioritise recovery actions for thousands of impacted plant species and animals.

It is also worth noting that more [than 87% of Australian plant species](#) occur only in Australia, so the impact of the 2019 and 2020 bushfires had global significance for plant conservation. This is why the database [AusTraits](#) — developed in partnership with the [Australian Research Data Commons](#) (ARDC) and 19 institutions and focusing on Australian plant trait data — was also crucial to recovery efforts. AusTraits data is also being [delivered](#) to the ALA and the [EcoCommons](#) platform, which benefits from co-investment mechanisms involving government, universities, and research partners.

Identifying important conservation areas

Gabon is home to [exceptional floristic diversity](#), with over 5,000 recorded plant species, and 85% of its territory is covered by tropical rainforest. At the same time, Gabon is known for having several threatened plant species and unique ecosystems that have previously been in danger from a lack of protection. Aside from the [creation of 13 National Parks in the early 2000s](#), no recent coordinated efforts existed to protect Gabon's biodiversity.

The [KBA Partnership](#) aligns closely with the [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) and maintains the [World Database of Key Biodiversity Areas](#) (KBAs). This initiative facilitates the systematic identification, mapping, monitoring, and conservation of Key Biodiversity Areas, which represent the most globally significant sites for biodiversity.

In 2024, Gabon identified [35 Key Biodiversity Areas](#) (KBAs) covering 24% of its national territory (110,432 km²) and including a range of critically endangered or endangered species of plants and animals. This marked a significant step toward the country's commitment to protect 30% of its land and marine areas by 2030. This assessment revealed that 16 KBAs lie outside the current protected area network.

The identification of KBAs has directly influenced national conservation policy and land-use planning. For example, the project created a foundation towards establishing a [national Red List working group](#); the KBAs were incorporated into [Gabon's National Land Allocation Plan](#); and the government is considering designating some of the 16 newly identified terrestrial KBAs as protected areas or Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs).

The results of the KBA identification exercise have also been compiled into a [220-page illustrated book](#) intended for land managers in government and local communities, the private sector and conservation actors, as well as anyone interested in discovering Gabon's biological diversity. Nicolas Texier, one of the book's authors emphasised:

"In our rapidly changing world, biological data must form the basis and core of all land use planning and management. To help scientists, land managers and decision-makers in planning and implementing biodiversity conservation strategies, this data must be made freely accessible and widely shared among stakeholders."

Conclusions

Modern biodata resources are transforming conservation practice by aggregating fragmented datasets, standardising formats and providing analytical tools that enable rapid assessment of biodiversity patterns and threats. These platforms empower not only researchers but also policymakers and land managers to make informed decisions about protecting the local biological heritage.

The case studies demonstrate that these resources deliver measurable benefits and play a critical role in crisis response and long-term planning alike. By promoting collaboration across governments, research institutions and communities, biodata resources are helping to safeguard the ecosystems upon which all life depends.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
Atlas of Living Australia	<p>The Atlas of Living Australia is Australia's national biodiversity database. It provides free, online access to information about Australia's biodiversity. It contains over 151 million occurrence records, and over 11,000 datasets.</p> <p>Alongside data, the resource also offers an interactive map detailing all species from animals, plants and fungi to bacteria and algae, according to a specific location. It supports research, environmental monitoring, conservation planning, education, and biosecurity activities, and is a great way to learn more about the biodiversity in your area.</p>
AusTraits	<p>AusTraits is an open-source, harmonised database of Australian plant trait data. It synthesises data on nearly 500 traits across more than 30,000 taxa from field campaigns, published literature, taxonomic monographs, and individual taxon descriptions.</p> <p>It began in 2016 as an initiative between three lab groups and it has grown to be the largest collation of plant trait data for Australian plants.</p>
EcoCommons	<p>EcoCommons is an ecological modelling platform and collaborative commons, providing access to more than 59,000 datasets and 20 algorithms. Alongside datasets, the site provides advanced modelling tools which support areas like species distribution modelling and visualisation of species occurrences and species trait data.</p>

Resources	About
<p><u>International Union for Conservation of Nature's Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN Red List)</u></p>	<p>The IUCN Red List is the most comprehensive resource on the global extinction risk status of animal, plant and fungus species. This resource was established in 1964 and currently holds data on over 163,000 species, with more than 45,300 species (28%) currently threatened with extinction.</p> <p>The resource is often referred to as a Barometer of Life and holds a wealth of information beyond the species and extinction risk status, such as population size, habitat and threats. Availability of this information can support conservation decisions and minimise the decline in biodiversity.</p>
<p><u>Species Observation System</u></p>	<p>The Species Observation System (SOS) is an open source application platform for aggregating and sharing datasets of species observations, developed and hosted by SLU Swedish Species Information Centre (SLU Adb).</p> <p>The SOS contains over 100 million species observations and collects these from a number of different data sources. The API supports searches of up to 10,000 records and retrieval of up to 2 million records.</p>
<p><u>The National Red List</u></p>	<p>The National Red List contains data on sub global species assessments of how endangered species are, based on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, providing more localised information than global data. The resource supports visualisation of the data through an interactive global map, by geographical area or species, as well as access to assessments and publications.</p>
<p><u>World Database of Key Biodiversity Areas</u></p>	<p>The World Database on Key Biodiversity Areas is a resource covering places in the world that are most important for species and their habitats. These span terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems. The data is hosted by IBAT and as of 2025, this resource covers 16,502 datasets.</p>

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